

Conformal invariance and the Lundgren-Monin-Novikov equations for vorticity fields in 2D turbulence: Refuting a recent claim

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Abstract

The recent claim by Grebenev *et al.* [*J. Phys. A: Math. Theor.* **50**, 435502 (2017)] that the inviscid 2D Lundgren-Monin-Novikov (LMN) equations on a zero vorticity characteristic naturally would reveal local conformal invariance when only analyzing these by means of a classical Lie-group symmetry approach, is invalid and will be refuted in the present comment. To note is that within this comment the (possible) existence of conformal invariance in 2D turbulence is not questioned, only the conclusion as is given in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) and their approach how this invariance was derived is what is being criticized and refuted herein. In fact, the algebraic derivation for conformal invariance of the 2D LMN vorticity equations in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) is flawed. A key constraint of the LMN equations has been wrongly transformed. Providing the correct transformation instead will lead to a breaking of the proclaimed conformal group. The corrected version of Grebenev *et al.* (2017) just leads to a globally constant scaling in the fields and not to a local one as claimed. In consequence, since in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) only the first equation within the infinite and unclosed LMN chain is considered, also different Lie-group infinitesimals for the one- and two-point probability density functions (PDFs) will result from this correction, replacing thus the misleading ones proposed.

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1. Summary of the key results obtained in Grebenev *et al.* (2017)

Considered is the first equation in the unclosed chain of the inviscid 2D Lundgren-Monin-Novikov (LMN) vorticity equations (Eq. [3])

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial f_1(\mathbf{x}, \omega, t)}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x^1} \int d^2 \mathbf{x}' d\omega' \omega' \frac{x^2 - x'^2}{2\pi |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|^2} f_2(\mathbf{x}, \omega, \mathbf{x}', \omega', t) \\ + \frac{\partial}{\partial x^2} \int d^2 \mathbf{x}' d\omega' \omega' \frac{x^1 - x'^1}{2\pi |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|^2} f_2(\mathbf{x}, \omega, \mathbf{x}', \omega', t) = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (1.1)$$

describing the dynamics of the 1-point probability density function (PDF) f_1 in terms of the (unclosed) 2-point PDF f_2 , where ω and ω' denote the sample space variables of the single vorticity component at the space-time points (\mathbf{x}, t) and (\mathbf{x}', t) , respectively. This equation (1.1) is supplemented by a normalization constraint for each of the two PDFs (Eq. [4])

$$\int d\omega f_1 = 1, \quad \int d\omega' f_2 = f_1. \quad (1.2)$$

Relations (1.1) and (1.2) form the complete set of equations which then were subjected to a systematic Lie-group symmetry analysis in Grebenev *et al.* (2017). By introducing the following vector of independent variables (Eq. [5])

$$(y^0, \mathbf{y}) = (t, \mathbf{y}) = (t, \mathbf{x}, \omega, \mathbf{x}', \omega') = (t, x^1, x^2, \omega, x'^1, x'^2, \omega'), \quad (1.3)$$

and by using this \mathbf{y} notation interchangeably with the original \mathbf{x} notation, this governing system

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of equations (1.1)-(1.2) can be equivalently rewritten as (Eqs. [6-7])

$$\mathbf{E}_1: \quad \frac{\partial J^0}{\partial y^0} + \frac{\partial J^1}{\partial y^1} + \frac{\partial J^2}{\partial y^2} = 0, \quad (1.4)$$

$$\mathbf{E}_2: \quad J^1 + \frac{1}{2\pi} \int d^2\mathbf{x}' d\omega' \omega' \frac{x^2 - x'^2}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|^2} f_2 = 0, \quad (1.5)$$

$$\mathbf{E}_3: \quad J^2 - \frac{1}{2\pi} \int d^2\mathbf{x}' d\omega' \omega' \frac{x^1 - x'^1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|^2} f_2 = 0, \quad (1.6)$$

$$\mathbf{E}_4: \quad 1 - \int d\omega f_1 = 0, \quad (1.7)$$

$$\mathbf{E}_5: \quad f_1 - \int d\omega' f_2 = 0, \quad (1.8)$$

where $J^0 := f_1$. The Lie-group symmetry analysis for the above system was performed successively in Grebenev *et al.* (2017), first for equation \mathbf{E}_1 , then by including \mathbf{E}_2 and \mathbf{E}_3 into the analysis, to then finally restrict the obtained symmetry result by \mathbf{E}_4 and \mathbf{E}_5 . To note is that only the first step, i.e. the symmetry analysis for \mathbf{E}_1 , was discussed generally, while all subsequent steps were performed under a specific Lie-point symmetry ansatz to explicitly bring forward a local conformal invariance for this system.

In infinitesimal form, the most general Lie-point symmetry admitted by \mathbf{E}_1 (1.4), being itself an equation in continuity form with four independent and three dependent variables, is given as (Eqs. [27-30])

$$\begin{aligned} X = & \xi^0(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \xi^1(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega) \frac{\partial}{\partial x^1} + \xi^2(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega) \frac{\partial}{\partial x^2} + \xi^3(\omega) \frac{\partial}{\partial \omega} \\ & + \eta^0(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega, \mathbf{J}) \frac{\partial}{\partial J^0} + \eta^1(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega, \mathbf{J}) \frac{\partial}{\partial J^1} + \eta^2(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega, \mathbf{J}) \frac{\partial}{\partial J^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (1.9)$$

with

$$\eta^i(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega, \mathbf{J}) = a_k^i(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega) J^k + b^i(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega), \quad i, k = 0, 1, 2, \quad (1.10)$$

where the coefficients a_k^i have the specified form

$$a_k^i = \xi_k^i - \delta_k^i (\xi_0^0 + \xi_1^1 + \xi_2^2 + C(\omega)), \quad \xi_k^i := \frac{\partial \xi^i}{\partial y^k}, \quad (1.11)$$

and where the b^i are arbitrary solutions of \mathbf{E}_1 (1.4). Note that while the three infinitesimals ξ^0 , ξ^1 and ξ^2 are arbitrary (1-point) space-time functions, the generating infinitesimal for the vorticity ξ^3 , however, is independent of space and time; it is an arbitrary function only of its own defining variable $y^3 = \omega$. This result stems from the fact that the variable $y^3 = \omega$ is not explicit in equation \mathbf{E}_1 (1.4) with the effect then that a symmetry analysis identifies it as a hidden parameter that only can be arbitrarily re-parametrized. In (1.11), function C is also only a function of ω not depending on space and time. The above result (1.9)-(1.11) has been independently validated by using the computer algebra package DESOLV-II of Vu *et al.* (2012), matching the result given in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) by Eqs. [27-30], up to the minor misprint¹ in the dependencies of the infinitesimals (instead of \mathbf{y} only \mathbf{x}, ω), the missing constraint $\xi_0^3 = 0$ in Eq. [30], and that $C \equiv C(\omega)$ — see Appendix A for an explicit proof of this result (1.9)-(1.11).

¹If claimed not to be a misprint, then it is definitely a mistake in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) to denote the dependencies of the infinitesimals in Eqs. [27-30] with \mathbf{y} instead of (\mathbf{x}, ω) . The reason is that if the J^i are formally identified as functions of \mathbf{y} , then equation \mathbf{E}_1 (1.4) has to be augmented by the 9 constraints $J_k^i = 0$, for $k = 4, 5, 6$, to indicate and to provide the relevant information that all J^i are 1-point and not 2-point functions.

Based on this result (1.9)-(1.11) for E_1 , the second step in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) includes the equations E_2 (1.5) and E_3 (1.6) into the symmetry analysis, however, not generally, but rather with the following specifically chosen ansatz for the infinitesimals (Eqs. [A.35-A.38])²

$$\xi^0 = 0, \quad (1.12)$$

$$\xi^1 = c^{11}(\mathbf{x})x^1 + c^{12}(\mathbf{x})x^2 + d^1(\mathbf{x}), \quad (1.13)$$

$$\xi^2 = c^{21}(\mathbf{x})x^1 + c^{22}(\mathbf{x})x^2 + d^2(\mathbf{x}), \quad (1.14)$$

$$\xi^4 = c^{11}(\mathbf{x})x'^1 + c^{12}(\mathbf{x})x'^2 + d^1(\mathbf{x}), \quad (1.15)$$

$$\xi^5 = c^{21}(\mathbf{x})x'^1 + c^{22}(\mathbf{x})x'^2 + d^2(\mathbf{x}), \quad (1.16)$$

along with the constraints (Eq. [A.40] leading to [A.41])

$$c^{22}(\mathbf{x}) = c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) \quad \text{and} \quad c^{21}(\mathbf{x}) = -c^{12}(\mathbf{x}), \quad (1.17)$$

which, as an overall result, already represents the structure of a local conformal invariance for the combined system E_1 - E_3 . Note that according to notation (1.3), the functions ξ^4 (1.15) and ξ^5 (1.16) represent the infinitesimals for the independent variables $y^4 = x'^1$ and $y^5 = x'^2$, respectively.

With the ansatz (1.12)-(1.17) and the result (1.9)-(1.11) for E_1 , a combined symmetry analysis for E_1 - E_3 inevitably leads to the relations (Eqs. [40-45])

$$d_1^1(\mathbf{x}) = 2c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) - c_1^{11}(\mathbf{x})x^1 - c_1^{12}(\mathbf{x})x^2, \quad (1.18)$$

$$d_2^1(\mathbf{x}) = -c_2^{11}(\mathbf{x})x^1 - c_2^{12}(\mathbf{x})x^2, \quad (1.19)$$

$$d_1^2(\mathbf{x}) = c_1^{12}(\mathbf{x})x^1 - c_1^{11}(\mathbf{x})x^2, \quad (1.20)$$

$$d_2^2(\mathbf{x}) = 2c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + c_2^{12}(\mathbf{x})x^1 - c_2^{11}(\mathbf{x})x^2, \quad (1.21)$$

with

$$3c_1^{11} = -c_2^{12}, \quad 3c_2^{11} = c_1^{12}, \quad \text{and hence: } c_{11}^{11} + c_{22}^{11} = 0, \quad c_{11}^{12} + c_{22}^{12} = 0, \quad (1.22)$$

and the further results (Eq. [39] and Eq. [52])³

$$\xi^6 = 2c^{11}(\mathbf{x})\omega', \quad (1.23)$$

$$\eta_{f_2} = -\left(8c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega)\right)f_2 + b'(t, \mathbf{y}), \quad (1.24)$$

where b' is an arbitrary solution to the equations E_2 and E_3 in correspondence to the two arbitrary solutions b^1 and b^2 given in (1.10) for E_1 , i.e.,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} b^1(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega) + \frac{1}{2\pi} \int d^2\mathbf{x}' d\omega' \omega' \frac{x^2 - x'^2}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|^2} b'(t, \mathbf{y}) &= 0, \\ b^2(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega) - \frac{1}{2\pi} \int d^2\mathbf{x}' d\omega' \omega' \frac{x^1 - x'^1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|^2} b'(t, \mathbf{y}) &= 0. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1.25)$$

To note is that the dependencies of the infinitesimals ξ^3 , η^0 , η^1 and η^2 in (1.9)-(1.10) stay unchanged after this extended analysis, i.e., augmenting the symmetry analysis for E_1 by including E_2 and E_3 does not restrict these infinitesimals any further; they simply are not effected and thus

²Note that the infinitesimal for the time variable ξ^0 in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) has been ultimately put to zero, not during the symmetry analysis itself, which therein was explicitly performed in Appx. A, but later when discussing the result in Sec. 3 on p. 8; see Eq. [33]. Thus, for convenience, ξ^0 is considered herein throughout as zero.

³Note that $C_1 + C_2$ in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) corresponds exactly to $C(\omega)$ in (1.11); see p. 16 where “the constant C [in Eq. 29 or A.4] was presented as a sum of the two constants $C = C_1 + C_2$ ”.

remain unchanged by this extension. Employing the specific ansatz (1.12)-(1.17) and the result (1.18)-(1.21), the latter three infinitesimals can at least be explicitly written out as (Eq. [51])

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \eta^0 &= -\left(6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega)\right) f_1 + b^0(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega), \\ \eta^1 &= -\left(3c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega)\right) J^1 + c^{12}(\mathbf{x}) J^2 + b^1(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega), \\ \eta^2 &= -c^{12}(\mathbf{x}) J^1 - \left(3c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega)\right) J^2 + b^2(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1.26)$$

Now, by including also the last two remaining equations into the symmetry analysis, namely the two consistency conditions E_4 (1.7) and E_5 (1.8), further restrictions for the infinitesimals can be expected. Including first the latter equation E_5 , we just obtain the trivial restriction (Eq. [53])

$$b^0(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega) = \int d\omega' b'(t, \mathbf{y}), \quad (1.27)$$

meaning that equation E_5 (1.8) already transforms as an invariant under the generating transformations (1.12)-(1.26). In other words, when taking along the constraint (1.27), equation E_5 is fully compatible to the already determined symmetries of subsystem E_1 - E_3 ; no symmetries are broken when augmenting this system by E_5 .

When including equation E_4 (1.7), however, the situation is different: Besides the trivial restriction (Eq. [53])⁴

$$\int d\omega b^0(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega) = 0, \quad (1.28)$$

we also obtain the crucial restriction⁵ (see Sec. 2.2 for a detailed proof)

$$\xi_3^3 = 6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega), \quad (1.29)$$

which forces the function c^{11} to be a constant now not depending on the spatial coordinate \mathbf{x} , simply because the left-hand side ξ_3^3 is, according to result (1.9), a function of ω only: $\xi^3 = \xi^3(\omega)$. Hence, since this result is globally valid for *all* $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$, *including* the case $\omega = 0$, the above restriction (1.29) is equivalent to the combined restriction⁶

$$c_1^{11}(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad c_2^{11}(\mathbf{x}) = 0, \quad \forall \omega \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (1.30)$$

which contradicts the ansatz made for ξ^3 (Eq. [38]) in Grebenev *et al.* (2017), where, also for the particular case of zero vorticity $\omega = 0$, this function is wrongly and misleadingly prescribed to be non-constant: $c_1^{11}(\mathbf{x}) \neq 0$ and $c_2^{11}(\mathbf{x}) \neq 0$.

Hence, due to this constraint (1.29), or equivalently due to (1.30), the local conformal invariance for E_1 - E_5 (1.4)-(1.8), which itself as a combined system represents the first equation in the infinite and unclosed hierarchy of LMN vorticity equations, cannot be confirmed as claimed in Grebenev *et al.* (2017), also not for the particular case $\omega = 0$.

Even if this proof is already fully sufficient to show that Grebenev *et al.* (2017) has been refuted, we will nevertheless examine their false and thus misleading conclusion in more detail in the next section, by looking at it from different perspectives in order to gain a better understanding of all the processes involved.

⁴Note that the explicit form of the restrictions (1.28) and (1.29) can also be represented differently, for example, when splitting the arbitrary function $C(\omega)$ additively into two separate ones $C(\omega) = C_1(\omega) + C_2(\omega)$, as has been done in Grebenev *et al.* (2017). For instance, if C_2 is linked to b^0 and C_1 to ξ^3 , then (1.28) and (1.29) can also be equivalently written as $\int d\omega b^0(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega) = \int d\omega C_2(\omega)$ and $\xi_3^3 = 6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C_1(\omega)$, respectively.

⁵Restriction (1.29) guarantees that the for the combined system E_1 - E_5 determined symmetry transformation is universally valid for *all* possible solutions of the 1-point PDF f_1 , which essentially is also the purpose of every symmetry analysis: To find transformations that leave equations invariant independent of the particular structure they may give as solutions for the dependent variables — see Sec. 2.2 for the derivation of (1.29) and for a more detailed discussion on that issue.

⁶Note that according to result (1.22), the constraint (1.30) also restricts its dual function $c^{12}(\mathbf{x})$ to be a constant: $c_1^{12}(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ and $c_2^{12}(\mathbf{x}) = 0$.

2. Revealing and correcting the mistake in Grebenev *et al.* (2017)

2.1. First perspective: The smoothness-axiom of Lie-groups

The heart of their non-correctible error in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) lies in the interplay between result Eq. [38] and Eq. [30]:

$$\xi^3 = [6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C_1]\omega, \quad (2.1)$$

$$\xi_1^3 = \xi_2^3 = 0. \quad (2.2)$$

The solution constraint (2.2) says that the infinitesimal ξ^3 , given by (2.1), should not depend on the spatial coordinates x^1 and x^2 . Sure, at first glance (2.1) and (2.2) stand in conflict with each other, because to force a persistent spatial dependence with (2.1) is obviously not compatible with the spatial independence as demanded by (2.2). But at a second glance, when particularly looking at the functional structure of (2.1), it seems that this conflict can be easily resolved if $\omega = 0$ is chosen, as the authors then did after Eq. [46].

Because now, with this specification $\omega = 0$, result (2.1) turns to $\xi^3 = 0$ with which (2.2) then turns into $0 = 0$ and which therefore, according to the rationale of Grebenev *et al.* (2017), can be successfully removed from the invariance group simply because this constraint (2.2) gets identically satisfied when evaluated at $\omega = 0$. That the constraint (2.2), i.e. Eq. [30], is indeed removed from the invariance group can be explicitly seen, e.g., in their incorrect final result Eq. [61] and its consequence Eq. [64], in that both these results do not come along with the constraint Eq. [30] anymore, or, in the flawed⁷ and misleading invariance proof of the probability measure μ in Sec. 3.3, which explicitly shows that Eq. [30] is not part of their proof anymore.

It's clear what the implications are when incorrectly removing constraint (2.2) from the invariance group for $\omega = 0$: The function c^{11} in (2.1) need not to be reduced to a global constant since it need not to comply with (2.2) anymore (due to its "non-restricting" form $0 = 0$), but can remain to be a general function on the spatial coordinates x^1 and x^2 , which then, along with the conditions Eqs. [44-45], allows for the desired conformal invariance Eqs. [34-37] not to get broken. But this reasoning is both wrong and seriously misleading as we will prove next.

2.1.1. Proof that constraint (2.2) may not be removed from invariance group even if $\omega = 0$

Even when putting $\omega = 0$ in order to enforce compatibility between (2.2) and (2.1), and the constraint (2.2) itself pretends to be in the non-restrictive form $0 = 0$, the authors do not have a magic wand to simply let (2.2) disappear from the invariance group. The constraint (2.2) is still there and active even after putting $\omega = 0$, simply because (2.2) is permanently valid for *all* real numbers of ω , and that without any restrictions, which eventually is a crucial information not explicitly mentioned by the authors. But what does this additional information imply now? Well, since (2.2) is *continuously* valid for *all* $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$ without any restrictions (which we will discuss at length further below and prove in detail in Appendix A), we can take, for example, any differential consequence of (2.2) according to this variable without restrictions, for which we will then get further combined constraint equations also *continuously* valid for *all* $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$, on account of the underlying smoothness-axiom of Lie-groups. For example, due to the global existence of (2.2)

$$\frac{\partial \xi^3}{\partial x^1} = \frac{\partial \xi^3}{\partial x^2} = 0, \quad \forall \omega \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (2.3)$$

we thus can imply the following differential consequence:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \xi^3}{\partial \omega \partial x^1} = \frac{\partial^2 \xi^3}{\partial \omega \partial x^2} = 0, \quad \forall \omega \in \mathbb{R} \quad \iff \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial x^1} \left(\frac{\partial \xi^3}{\partial \omega} \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x^2} \left(\frac{\partial \xi^3}{\partial \omega} \right) = 0, \quad \forall \omega \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (2.4)$$

⁷An independent proof for this claim will be given in the next section, Sec. 2.2.

The right-hand side of this implication (2.4) tells us now that the function $\xi_3^3 := \partial_\omega \xi^3$ should not depend on the spatial coordinates x^1 and x^2 for *any* value of ω as well, i.e.,

$$\frac{\partial \xi_3^3}{\partial x^1} = \frac{\partial \xi_3^3}{\partial x^2} = 0, \quad \forall \omega \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (2.5)$$

where initially in (2.4), and this is important, we explicitly made use of the smoothness-axiom of Lie-groups which allows for the interchanging of partial derivatives on its elements.

Hence, besides ξ^3 , also ξ_3^3 should be spatially independent for *any* value of ω , including $\omega = 0$. But this result causes a problem now. While the space-dependent result (2.1)

$$\xi^3 = [6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C_1]\omega, \quad (2.6)$$

could still be made compatible with constraint (2.3) by choosing $\omega = 0$, this clearly does not work anymore for the next higher-order constraint (2.5), since ξ^3 is linear in ω . Inserting (2.6) into (2.5) then leads to

$$\frac{\partial c^{11}(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x^1} = \frac{\partial c^{11}(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x^2} = 0, \quad \forall \omega \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (2.7)$$

which will reduce the spatial function c^{11} to a global constant and thus, as a final result, the desired conformal invariance is broken, in particular also for $\omega = 0$. \square

It's clear that the crucial aspect to obtain the above result (2.5) is that (2.2) has to be valid for *all* $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$, as explicitly and transparently written in (2.3):

$$\frac{\partial \xi^3}{\partial x^1} = \frac{\partial \xi^3}{\partial x^2} = 0, \quad \forall \omega \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Indeed, this unrestricted condition on constraint (2.2), namely that ξ^3 is globally independent on the spatial coordinates for any ω , we already have given the proof through result (1.9)-(1.11), a result that is shared⁸ by Grebenev *et al.* (2017), but in its consequence has not been interpreted correctly by them. The correct interpretation of result (1.9) is that ξ^3 shows no other dependence than solely on ω and that this dependence is unrestricted, i.e., it is not constrained by any hidden or explicit condition on ω :

$$\xi^3 \equiv \xi^3(\omega), \text{ unrestrictedly for all } \omega \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (2.8)$$

In other words, when performing a thorough symmetry investigation, as we did to obtain the correct result (1.9)-(1.11), it shows that the constraint Eq. [30] as given in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) is not complete. It correctly has to be extended to:

$$\xi_1^3 = \xi_2^3 = \xi_4^3 = \xi_5^3 = \xi_6^3 = \xi_0^3 = 0, \quad \forall \omega \in \mathbb{R}, \quad \text{while } \xi_3^3 \neq 0. \quad (2.9)$$

To avoid any misunderstandings of this result, the following should be noted: Constraint (2.9) is *not* an assumption, but the result of a thorough symmetry investigation, which we carefully checked both by hand as well as by using third-party computer software⁹ that systematically calculates all Lie group symmetries of differential equations automatically. Because (2.9) is essentially nothing else than the full symmetry solution for the infinitesimal ξ^3 of the local (differential) part of the considered system, which in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) is given by Eq. [6] and herein by (1.4). But Grebenev *et al.* (2017) failed to give the full symmetry solution, simply because the decisive and crucial information $\forall \omega \in \mathbb{R}$ of result (2.9) is missing and thus not part of their solution as they derived it in Sec. A.1.

⁸Up to the concern stated in footnote no.1, p. 2.

⁹In Appendix A we provide an explicit proof of (2.9), in that we perform a complete invariance analysis of the defining local equation E_1 (1.4) that results to (2.9).

2.2. Second perspective: Non-invariance of the normalization condition E_4

When performing a Lie-group symmetry analysis on the governing equation E_1 (1.4), it provides us with two strong results: (i) The infinitesimal ξ^3 (1.9) is only a function of its defining vorticity variable: $\xi^3 = \xi^3(\omega)$, and (ii) the infinitesimals η^i (1.10) for the dependent variables can be supplemented by a function C (1.11), depending also only on the vorticity variable: $C = C(\omega)$. In particular, when augmenting the symmetry analysis by also including the remaining equations E_2 - E_5 , this twofold result from E_1 is of global nature, meaning that ξ^3 and C should and may not depend on the spatial variable \mathbf{x} for *all* $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$, including also the zero vorticity case $\omega = 0$.

In Grebenev *et al.* (2017), however, the following unexplained and misleading ansatz for ξ^3 is made (Eq. [38]):

$$\xi^3 = \left(6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C_1\right)\omega, \quad \text{for } c_1^{11}(\mathbf{x}) \neq 0 \text{ and } c_2^{11}(\mathbf{x}) \neq 0, \quad (2.10)$$

which obviously, as explained above, is not compatible with the symmetry result as stipulated by the governing equation E_1 (1.4). The argument in Grebenev *et al.* (2017), however, is that for the specific case $\omega = 0$ this conflict is resolved. Although this argument itself is correct, since a zero infinitesimal $\xi^3 = 0$ is inherently independent of any variables whatsoever, they overlooked the fact that their *local* condition, which just only holds for the single value $\omega = 0$, cannot be employed to transform the normalization condition E_4 (1.7), which obviously constitutes a *non-local* constraint equation.¹⁰ The reason is that E_4 is a global relation that sums over *all* vorticity values $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$, and not only locally for $\omega = 0$. To therefore correctly transform this global constraint E_4

$$\int d\omega f_1 = 1, \quad (2.11)$$

where ω needs to be varied by $d\omega$ over the whole (infinite) integration range, one has to use a transformation rule for ω that is globally valid for all values, and not only for the fixed value $\omega = 0$. Hence, to invariantly transform (2.11) in line with E_1 , the transformation rule (2.10) is not the correct choice, since it is only valid for $\omega = 0$ and thus, as a fixed single value, cannot be varied in ω , while for $\omega \neq 0$, as already said, rule (2.10) has to be discarded, simply because it is incompatible to the existing constraint $\xi_1^3 = \xi_2^3 = 0$, that means incompatible to the general result $\xi^3 = \xi^3(\omega)$ for E_1 to be invariant.

Hence it is clear that only the following globally valid ansatz (up to order $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)$ in the group parameter ϵ)

$$\tilde{\omega} = \omega + \epsilon \cdot \xi^3(\omega), \quad \forall \omega \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (2.12)$$

will invariantly transform the global constraint E_4 (2.11) in line with E_1 . The associated infinitesimal constraint that will be induced as result then has the form

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= 1 - \int d\tilde{\omega} \tilde{f}_1 = 1 - \int d\omega \left| \frac{\partial \tilde{\omega}}{\partial \omega} \right| (f_1 + \epsilon \eta^0 + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)) \stackrel{(2.12)}{=} 1 - \int d\omega |1 + \epsilon \xi_3^3| (f_1 + \epsilon \eta^0) + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2) \\ &\stackrel{\epsilon \ll 1}{=} 1 - \int d\omega (1 + \epsilon \xi_3^3) (f_1 + \epsilon \eta^0) + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2) = 1 - \int d\omega (f_1 + \epsilon (\eta^0 + \xi_3^3 f_1)) + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2) \\ &\stackrel{(1.26)}{=} 1 - \int d\omega (f_1 + \epsilon (-6c^{11} f_1 - C f_1 + b^0 + \xi_3^3 f_1)) + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2) \\ &\stackrel{(1.28) \& (2.11)}{=} \int d\omega (6c^{11} + C - \xi_3^3) f_1 + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon), \end{aligned} \quad (2.13)$$

¹⁰The same mistake also has been made in Sec. 3.3 in Grebenev *et al.* (2017), which, if corrected, invalidates their claim that the probability measure $\mu(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega) = f_1(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega) d\omega$ is local-conformally invariant. On the one side their mistake is that Eq. [38] for $\omega \neq 0$ *may not* be used to transform μ since it is inconsistent to the symmetry transform of the governing Eq. [6], and on the other side their mistake is that Eq. [38] for $\omega = 0$ *cannot* be used to transform μ since ω is then rigidly fixed and thus not variable anymore.

which, if we seek for a symmetry transformation that is valid for *all* possible solutions f_1 , is equivalent to the constraint (1.29)

$$6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega) - \xi_3^3(\omega) = 0, \quad (2.14)$$

that now forces c^{11} to be a constant,¹¹ due to that ξ^3 , according to the rule (2.12), is only a function of ω not depending on \mathbf{x} . \square

As exercised in Grebenev *et al.* (2017), which again refers to Ibragimov *et al.* (2002), the determining equation (2.14) can also be derived alternatively by noting that the non-local determining symmetry equation (2.13) can be split with respect to group variable f_1 using variational differentiation. Since the bracketed term in (2.13) does not depend on f_1 , taking the variational or functional derivative ($\delta/\delta f_1(\bar{\omega})$) of this equation then leads to the same local result (2.14):

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \frac{\delta}{\delta f_1(\bar{\omega})} \int d\omega (6c^{11} + C - \xi_3^3) f_1 \\ &= \int d\omega (6c^{11} + C - \xi_3^3) \delta(\omega - \bar{\omega}) = 6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C|_{\omega=\bar{\omega}} - \xi_3^3|_{\omega=\bar{\omega}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.15)$$

Note here that it is valid to take the variational derivative of equation (2.13) since f_1 can be *continuously* varied to still satisfy equation (2.13) by just choosing the non-constant coefficient or pre-factor of f_1 appropriately, trivially of course as (2.14). In contrast of course to the defining equation (2.11) itself, which determines or fixes f_1 and which thus cannot be continuously varied: Any arbitrary non-zero functional variation of f_1 will violate the constraint (2.11), as can be clearly seen by taking the variational derivative ($\delta/\delta f_1(\bar{\omega})$) of this constraint

$$0 = \frac{\delta}{\delta f_1(\bar{\omega})} \left(-1 + \int d\omega f_1 \right) = \int d\omega \delta(\omega - \bar{\omega}) = 1, \quad (2.16)$$

turning the constraint (2.11) thus into the contradiction $1 = 0$. This conflict just tells us that equation (2.11) cannot be functionally varied simply because it defines and determines the function f_1 , similar as in the usual variation for real numbers if we would fix a variable to a certain value, say $x = 1$, then any variation on it would be meaningless, since x is defined or determined strictly as 1. Evidently, taking the variation of $x = 1$ leads to the same conflict

$$0 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (-1 + x) = 1, \quad (2.17)$$

as in (2.16) for the functional variation of the defining and determining equation (2.11) for f_1 .

Back again to the general result (2.14) by choosing $\xi^3 = 0$, as it would be the case in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) when applying in Eq. [38] their necessary zero-vorticity constraint $\omega = 0$ (Eq. [32]), we note that their results for the infinitesimals η^0 and η' as given by Eqs. [51-52] are incorrect. Instead of an unrestricted $C = C_1 + C_2$, the constant restriction $C = -6c^{11}$ has to be used in their results in order to be consistent with $\xi^3 = 0$, exactly as it is required by (2.14). Hence, for $\xi^3 = 0$, the correct generating infinitesimals for f_1 and f_2 are given by (1.26) & (1.24)

$$\eta_{f_1} \equiv \eta^0 = b^0(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega), \quad \eta_{f_2} \equiv \eta' = -2c^{11} f_2 + b'(t, \mathbf{y}), \quad \forall \omega \in \mathbb{R}, \quad c_1^{11} = c_2^{11} = 0, \quad (2.18)$$

and not by Eqs. [51-52] as proposed in Grebenev *et al.* (2017). Note, since $C = -6c^{11}$ itself is a ω -independent choice, result (2.18) is in fact globally valid for all $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$. Regarding Sec. 3.3 in Grebenev *et al.* (2017), it is thus clear that for the above choice $\xi^3 = 0$, $\forall \omega \in \mathbb{R}$, and its resulting transform (2.18), the probability measure $\mu = f_1 d\omega$ (Eq. [68]) remains to be invariant, but not local-conformally anymore as claimed since c^{11} , according to (2.18), is a spatial constant now.

¹¹Another independent but equivalent argument that c^{11} needs to be a constant is to recognize that the non-local determining equation (2.13) is living in a jet space where \mathbf{x} and f_1 are jet coordinates defined by the underlying symmetry analysis of the governing system (1.1)-(1.2), i.e., a particular designed space where \mathbf{x} and f_1 are defined to each other as independents: $\partial_{x^1} f_1 = \partial_{x^2} f_1 = 0$. Then, by re-writing (2.13) as $6c^{11} + \int d\omega (C - \xi_3^3) f_1 = 0$ (since c^{11} by construction is independent of ω) and by taking the spatial derivatives on both sides, one directly obtains the overall consistent result $c_1^{11} = c_2^{11} = 0$, simply due to that C and ξ^3 on the one side are independent functions of \mathbf{x} and on the other that f_1 is a jet variable with respect to \mathbf{x} . — On jet spaces in general, see e.g. Olver (1993).

2.3. Third perspective: The non-exceptional role of $\omega = 0$

It is clear that when analyzing any system of equations on symmetries, as for example for the case E_1 - E_5 (1.4)-(1.8) considered herein, the symmetry result should not depend on the choice which subsystem is considered first and in which order it is being evaluated, i.e., no matter which direction in evaluation one takes, a symmetry analysis should always give exactly the same result, otherwise a consistent analysis is not guaranteed. For example, let us first consider the following approach: Before starting any analysis, we already specify the coordinate ω in the subsystem E_1 - E_3 & E_5 to an arbitrary but fixed value, say $\omega = \omega^*$, where $\omega^* \in \mathbb{R}$ can be any value from real space, including the choice $\omega^* = 0$. The initial system E_1 - E_5 (1.4)-(1.8) then turns into the form

$$E_1^*: \quad \frac{\partial J^{*0}}{\partial y^0} + \frac{\partial J^{*1}}{\partial y^1} + \frac{\partial J^{*2}}{\partial y^2} = 0, \quad (2.19)$$

$$E_2^*: \quad J^{*1} + \frac{1}{2\pi} \int d^2 \mathbf{x}' d\omega' \omega' \frac{x^2 - x'^2}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|^2} f_2^* = 0, \quad (2.20)$$

$$E_3^*: \quad J^{*2} - \frac{1}{2\pi} \int d^2 \mathbf{x}' d\omega' \omega' \frac{x^1 - x'^1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|^2} f_2^* = 0, \quad (2.21)$$

$$E_4: \quad 1 - \int d\omega f_1 = 0, \quad (2.22)$$

$$E_5^*: \quad f_1^* - \int d\omega' f_2^* = 0, \quad (2.23)$$

where (J^{*i}, f_2^*) are the functions (J^i, f_2) evaluated at $\omega = \omega^*$:

$$f_1^* \equiv J^{*0} = J^0|_{\omega=\omega^*} \equiv f_1|_{\omega=\omega^*}, \quad J^{*1;2} = J^{1;2}|_{\omega=\omega^*}, \quad f_2^* = f_2|_{\omega=\omega^*}. \quad (2.24)$$

Instead of 11 jet coordinates $(y^0, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{J}, f_2)$ for the initial system (1.4)-(1.8), a symmetry analysis of (2.19)-(2.23) now defines an extended jet space with 12 coordinates $(y^0, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{J}^*, f_2^*, f_1)$, where the additional coordinate f_1 is related to J^{*0} via (2.24). Formally, the four equations E_1^* - E_3^* & E_5^* can now be identified as a system being independent of the jet coordinate $y^3 = \omega$. Performing a symmetry analysis on this reduced subsystem for the ansatz (1.12)-(1.17), one yields the same results (1.18)-(1.27) as before in just replacing the ω -dependent infinitesimals (η^i, η_{f_2}) in (1.26) and (1.24) by their corresponding ω -independent infinitesimals $(\eta^{*i}, \eta_{f_2}^*)$:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \eta^{*0} &= -(6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C^*)f_1^* \equiv \eta_{f_1}^*, \\ \eta^{*1} &= -(3c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C^*)J^{*1} + c^{12}(\mathbf{x})J^{*2}, \\ \eta^{*2} &= -c^{12}(\mathbf{x})J^{*1} - (3c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C^*)J^{*2}, \\ \eta_{f_2}^* &= -(8c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C^*)f_2^*, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.25)$$

where C^* is any arbitrary constant and where, for simplicity and convenience, the solutions b^{*i} and b^{*l} were chosen as the trivial zero solutions, simply because of not being relevant here for the present discussion on consistency. Now, in using the defining relation (2.24), we can read off the unreduced infinitesimal η^0 for the jet coordinate f_1 from (2.25) as¹²

$$\eta^0 = -(6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega))f_1 \equiv \eta_{f_1}, \quad (2.26)$$

which is necessary now in order to find the infinitesimal $\xi^3 \equiv \xi_\omega$ from the last and remaining equation E_4 (2.22) in this system. Obviously, since (2.26) matches the result (1.26), the symmetry

¹² C^* in (2.25) is then defined as the evaluation $C(\omega)|_{\omega=\omega^*} \equiv C^*$.

analysis of E_4 (2.22) is identical to the one performed in the previous section (2.13), with the same result (2.14), however, now without any constraints on the infinitesimal ξ^3 :

$$6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega) - \xi_3^3(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega) = 0, \quad (2.27)$$

i.e., where ξ^3 can freely depend now on all independent variables involved,¹³ simply because the constructed ω -independence of the newly defined local equation E_1^* (2.19) cannot give or lead to any restrictions on ξ^3 , as it was the case before for the ω -dependent local equation E_1 (1.4).

Solving (2.27) explicitly for ξ^3 , the only solution that is in accordance or in line with subsystem E_1^* - E_3^* & E_5^* is given by the particular solution

$$\xi_3^3(t, \mathbf{x}, \omega) = \left(6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega)\right)(\omega - \omega^*) - \int_{\omega^*}^{\omega} \frac{dC(\bar{\omega})}{d\bar{\omega}}(\bar{\omega} - \omega^*) d\bar{\omega}, \quad (2.28)$$

since for $\omega = \omega^*$ this infinitesimal turns zero $\xi_3^3|_{\omega=\omega^*} = 0$, with the effect then that under this transformation the value $\omega = \omega^*$ gets mapped to the same value again: $\omega^* = \omega \mapsto \tilde{\omega} = \omega^*$, and therefore keeping subsystem E_1^* - E_3^* & E_5^* thus invariant.

Hence, it seems that the analysis of Grebenev *et al.* (2017) just got generalized to arbitrary vorticity isolines, since the result (2.28) is not restricted to the particular value of a zero-vorticity isoline $\omega^* = 0$, as in Eq. [38] in Grebenev *et al.* (2017). Hence we could say that we have shown local conformal invariance for the 2D LMN vorticity equations (up to second order in the LMN chain of equations) on all its vorticity isolines, that is, for all values of $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$. But, unfortunately, that is not the case. Because, when looking again at the determining equation (2.27) when evaluated at $\omega = \omega^*$ and equivalently re-written as

$$\xi_3^3|_{\omega=\omega^*} = 6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega^*), \quad \text{where } \xi_{31}^3 \neq 0, \quad \xi_{32}^3 \neq 0, \quad (2.29)$$

which in this section was obtained by first putting ω to a fixed value ω^* and then by performing a symmetry analysis, this equation (2.29) only constitutes an overall consistent equation if the same result is also obtained when reversing this procedure: First by performing a symmetry analysis and then by specifying $\omega = \omega^*$. For this reverse direction, however, the governing equations are E_1 - E_5 (1.4)-(1.8), for which the corresponding result to (2.29) is then given by (2.14)

$$\xi_3^3|_{\omega=\omega^*} = 6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega^*), \quad \text{where } \xi_{31}^3 = \xi_{32}^3 = 0. \quad (2.30)$$

The decisive difference between these two equations (2.29) and (2.30) is that their left-hand sides show different dependencies: While the left-hand side of (2.29) depends in general on \mathbf{x} , the left-hand side of (2.30) is strictly independent of \mathbf{x} . Hence, in order to obtain a consistent result for ξ_3^3 , the spatial function $c^{11}(\mathbf{x})$ has to be reduced to a constant, i.e., $c_1^{11} = c_2^{11} = 0$; only then can the two equations (2.29) and (2.30) be matched. This completes the third independent proof, demonstrating again that local conformal invariance cannot be confirmed as proclaimed in Grebenev *et al.* (2017), de facto disproving their claim not only for the zero-vorticity isoline but also for all non-zero ones. \square

2.4. Fourth perspective: Validating potential solutions via integral consequences

In this approach we assume that we have a solution for the 1-point and 2-point PDF (f_1, f_2) , obtained, for example, by a direct numerical simulation (DNS) of the (inviscid) deterministic Navier-Stokes equations for some specific unbounded flow configuration. Obviously, this solution (f_1, f_2) will then satisfy identically its defining PDF equations E_1 - E_5 (1.4)-(1.8). The question now is whether this solution remains to be solution of this system E_1 - E_5 (1.4)-(1.8) when being transformed on a zero-vorticity isoline according to the local conformal rule as proposed in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) (Eqs. [33-45,51-52]). The answer is obtained by augmenting the defining

¹³Note that since ξ^3 is associated to the 1-point quantity f_1 there is no dependence on any 2-point coordinates.

system E_1 - E_5 by certain integral consequences. For example, it is trivial to conclude that if the existing and available solution (f_1, f_2) satisfies the differential equation E_1 (1.4) along with the constraint E_4 (1.7) identically, then it also satisfies identically its integral consequence

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \int d\omega \left(\frac{\partial J^0}{\partial y^0} + \frac{\partial J^1}{\partial y^1} + \frac{\partial J^2}{\partial y^2} \right) \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial y^0} \underbrace{\int d\omega J^0}_{\substack{= 1 \\ (1.7)}} + \int d\omega \left(\frac{\partial J^1}{\partial y^1} + \frac{\partial J^2}{\partial y^2} \right) \equiv \frac{\partial}{\partial y^1} M^1 + \frac{\partial}{\partial y^2} M^2, \end{aligned} \quad (2.31)$$

where the M^i are defined as: $M^i = \int d\omega J^i$, $i = 1, 2$. Hence, in the following we will consider the following augmented system

$$E_1^*: \quad \frac{\partial J^{*0}}{\partial y^0} + \frac{\partial J^{*1}}{\partial y^1} + \frac{\partial J^{*2}}{\partial y^2} = 0, \quad (2.32)$$

$$E_{11}: \quad \frac{\partial M^1}{\partial y^1} + \frac{\partial M^2}{\partial y^2} = 0, \quad (2.33)$$

$$E_{12}: \quad M^1 - \int d\omega J^1 = 0, \quad (2.34)$$

$$E_{13}: \quad M^2 - \int d\omega J^2 = 0, \quad (2.35)$$

$$E_2^*: \quad J^{*1} + \frac{1}{2\pi} \int d^2\mathbf{x}' d\omega' \omega' \frac{x^2 - x'^2}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|^2} f_2^* = 0, \quad (2.36)$$

$$E_3^*: \quad J^{*2} - \frac{1}{2\pi} \int d^2\mathbf{x}' d\omega' \omega' \frac{x^1 - x'^1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|^2} f_2^* = 0, \quad (2.37)$$

$$E_4: \quad 1 - \int d\omega f_1 = 0, \quad (2.38)$$

$$E_5^*: \quad f_1^* - \int d\omega' f_2^* = 0, \quad (2.39)$$

which consistently extends the initial system of equations E_1 - E_5 (1.4)-(1.8) without changing the associated solution space. Note that we here proceed as in the previous section (viz. the third perspective), where already before the upcoming symmetry analysis the above subsystem (E_1, E_2, E_3, E_5) is formally reduced to the ω -independent subsystem $(E_1^*, E_2^*, E_3^*, E_5^*)$ in that the coordinate ω got again specified to some arbitrary but fixed value $\omega = \omega^*$, where $\omega^* \in \mathbb{R}$, including thus also again the zero-value choice $\omega^* = 0$ as in Grebenev *et al.* (2017).

Now, knowing that a symmetry analysis of this reduced system $(E_1^*, E_2^*, E_3^*, E_5^*)$ results to (2.25), we can read off again from the underlying consistency relation (2.24) the corresponding unreduced infinitesimals as¹⁴

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \eta^0 &= -\left(6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega)\right) f_1, \\ \eta^1 &= -\left(3c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega)\right) J^1 + c^{12}(\mathbf{x}) J^2, \\ \eta^2 &= -c^{12}(\mathbf{x}) J^1 - \left(3c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega)\right) J^2, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.40)$$

¹⁴It is obvious that (2.40) matches again the result (1.26). For simplicity and convenience, the solutions b^i and b^j were chosen as the trivial zero solutions, simply because they are not relevant for the discussion to be demonstrated herein.

which are necessary now to determine the infinitesimals ξ^3 and η_{M^i} from the four remaining equations E_{11} - E_{13} (2.33)-(2.35) and E_4 (2.38). Demanding their invariance, one obtains the following determining equations for η_{M^1} , η_{M^2} and ξ^3 :

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \eta_{M^1}}{\partial y^1} + \frac{\partial \eta_{M^2}}{\partial y^2} &= 0, & \frac{\partial \eta_{M^1}}{\partial M^1} - \frac{\partial \xi^1}{\partial y^1} - \frac{\partial \eta_{M^2}}{\partial M^2} + \frac{\partial \xi^2}{\partial y^2} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial \eta_{M^1}}{\partial M^2} - \frac{\partial \xi^1}{\partial y^2} &= 0, & \frac{\partial \eta_{M^2}}{\partial M^1} - \frac{\partial \xi^2}{\partial y^1} &= 0, & \frac{\partial \xi^1}{\partial M^1} + \frac{\partial \xi^2}{\partial M^2} &= 0, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.41)$$

$$\eta_{M^1} - \int d\omega(\eta^1 + \xi_3^3 J^1) = 0, \quad \eta_{M^2} - \int d\omega(\eta^2 + \xi_3^3 J^2) = 0, \quad \int d\omega(\eta^0 + \xi_3^3 J^0) = 0, \quad (2.42)$$

where (2.41) results from equation E_{11} (2.33), and (2.42) from E_{12} (2.34), E_{13} (2.35) and E_4 (2.38), respectively. In line with the already obtained symmetry result (2.40) of subsystem $(E_1^*, E_2^*, E_3^*, E_5^*)$, the last equation in (2.42) induces the already well-known relation (2.27)

$$\xi_3^3 = 6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega), \quad \text{where } \xi_{31}^3 \neq 0, \quad \xi_{32}^3 \neq 0, \quad (2.43)$$

which, when inserted along with (2.40) into the two former equations of (2.42), then gives the solution for the infinitesimals η_{M^i} explicitly as:

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_{M^1} &= \int d\omega(\eta^1 + \xi_3^3 J^1) \\ &= \int d\omega\left(- (3c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega))J^1 + c^{12}(\mathbf{x})J^2 + (6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega))J^1\right) \\ &= \int d\omega\left(3c^{11}(\mathbf{x})J^1 + c^{12}(\mathbf{x})J^2\right) \stackrel{(2.34) \& (2.35)}{=} 3c^{11}(\mathbf{x})M^1 + c^{12}(\mathbf{x})M^2, \end{aligned} \quad (2.44)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_{M^2} &= \int d\omega(\eta^2 + \xi_3^3 J^2) \\ &= \int d\omega\left(- c^{12}(\mathbf{x})J^1 - (3c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega))J^2 + (6c^{11}(\mathbf{x}) + C(\omega))J^2\right) \\ &= \int d\omega\left(- c^{12}(\mathbf{x})J^1 + 3c^{11}(\mathbf{x})J^2\right) \stackrel{(2.34) \& (2.35)}{=} -c^{12}(\mathbf{x})M^1 + 3c^{11}(\mathbf{x})M^2. \end{aligned} \quad (2.45)$$

However, this result is inconsistent to the determining equations given by (2.41), as can be seen by evaluating already the first equation¹⁵

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \frac{\partial \eta_{M^1}}{\partial y^1} + \frac{\partial \eta_{M^2}}{\partial y^2} \\ &= 3c_1^{11}M^1 + c_1^{12}M^2 - c_2^{12}M^1 + 3c_2^{11}M^2 \stackrel{(1.22)}{=} 6c_1^{11}M^1 + 6c_2^{11}M^2 \neq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (2.46)$$

The above relation can only be made consistent if the spatial function $c^{11}(\mathbf{x})$ is reduced to a global constant, i.e., if $c_1^{11} = c_2^{11} = 0$, thus eventually breaking the local conformal invariance of the subsystem $(E_1^*, E_2^*, E_3^*, E_5^*)$, where this breaking occurs not only for the specific value $\omega^* = 0$, but again for all real values $\omega^* \in \mathbb{R}$.

This result finally also answers our question stated in the beginning, namely whether the local conformal transformation as proposed in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) will map a given solution on a zero-vorticity isoline to a new solution. The answer is clearly no,¹⁶ simply because this particularly considered transformation constitutes no invariant transformation of the LMN vorticity equations; only the reduced case $c_1^{11} = c_2^{11} = 0$ constitutes one. This completes the fourth and final independent proof that refutes the key claims made by Grebenev *et al.* (2017). \square

¹⁵In fact, it is only the first equation in (2.41) that is inconsistent. The four other equations evaluate identically to zero for the considered ansatz (1.12)-(1.22).

¹⁶In particular, if the set of functions $M^i = \int d\omega J^i$ is a solution, then the local-conformally transformed set $\tilde{M}^i = \int d\tilde{\omega} \tilde{J}^i$ by Grebenev *et al.* (2017) is not a solution anymore, since the governing equation E_{11} (2.33) does not stay invariant under this transformation; only for the reduced case $c_1^{11} = c_2^{11} = 0$ it will stay invariant.

3. Final remarks

R1. On p. 8 in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) the following is said: “*It is interesting to note that (32) and (44) can be derived substituting the forms (33)-(39) into the infinitesimal form of equation (6).*” This statement is incorrect and misleading since Eq. [32], i.e., $\omega = 0$, is an external constraint that cannot be derived. Indeed, in their subsequent proof on p. 9, the existence of Eq. [32] is not derived but instead used again as an independent and exogenous condition.

R2. In Sec. 2.2 we have consistently proven that the first normalization constraint of Eq. [4] in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) in effect breaks their proposed conformal invariance, thus refuting their claim that the conclusion of a conformally invariant measure “*results from the presently conducted Lie group analysis (see appendix) that the first equation from (4) is also invariant*” [p. 12]. In fact, their analysis is flawed and does not allow for such a conclusion.

To note here is that it’s not a minor issue that the normalization condition Eq. [4] breaks the considered conformal invariance, e.g., by saying then let’s ignore the normalization condition from the system in order to restore this invariance. The normalization condition cannot be ignored, because it’s an internal condition that permanently guarantees that any PDF solution f_n stays physically meaningful during its evolution. In other words, if an invariance operator for the PDF system, as given in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) by Eq. [3], is not compatible to the normalization condition Eq. [4], then physical solutions can get mapped to unphysical ones. Therefore the normalization is an important ingredient in any PDF system and should be respected within a symmetry analysis. The same is true for all other internal constraints that go along with such a PDF system, all necessary to ensure physical PDF solutions. In this regard, please see our comment Frewer *et al.* (2017), which criticizes an earlier publication by V. Grebenev (Waclawczyk *et al.*, 2017), in that new invariance groups get proposed therein which obviously are not compatible to the full PDF system when including all internal constraints, i.e., ultimately, in Waclawczyk *et al.* (2017) non-physical symmetries are getting proposed.

R3. The following statement in Grebenev *et al.* (2017) on p. 8, that “*the relationships (46) also demonstrate the exceptional role of the zero-vorticity constraint (32) to guarantee that c^{11} and c^{12} are harmonic functions*”, is misleading. In Sec. 2.3 we clearly demonstrated that the choice $\omega = 0$ is not exceptional at all, because the obtained invariances can always be equivalently re-formulated such that *any* arbitrary but fixed value of $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$ will do the same job as the particular choice $\omega = 0$ — see again the result (2.28) for an alternative ξ^3 and its subsequent discussion. Hence, the choice of a zero-vorticity constraint $\omega = 0$ plays no exceptional role, with the result again of Sec. 2.3 that the proposed conformal invariance is not only broken for $\omega = 0$, but for all $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$, thus refuting Grebenev *et al.* (2017) in its most general form.

R4. Important to note in this overall discussion is that the invariant transformation examined in this investigation (1.12)-(1.30)¹⁷ is only an equivalence and not a true symmetry transformation, simply due to that we are dealing here with an unclosed system of equations (1.1)-(1.2) where the dynamical rule for the 2-point PDF f_2 is not known beforehand. In contrast to a true symmetry transformation, which maps a solution of a specific (closed) equation to a new solution of the same equation, an equivalence transform acts in a weaker sense in that it only maps an (unclosed) equation to a new (unclosed) equation of the same class.¹⁸ Of course, it is trivial and

¹⁷Note that only the reduced case $c_1^{11} = c_2^{11} = 0$ constitutes an invariant transformation.

¹⁸Equivalence transformations can be successfully applied for example to classify unclosed differential equations according to the number of symmetries they admit when specifying the unclosed terms (see e.g. Meleshko (2002); Khabirov & Ünal (2002a,b); Chirkunov (2012); Meleshko & Moyo (2015); Bihlo & Popovych (2017)). A typical task in this context sometimes is to find a specification of the unclosed terms such that the maximal symmetry algebra is gained. Once the equation is closed by a such a group classification, invariant solutions can be determined. But in how far these equations and their solutions are physically relevant and whether they can be matched to empirical data is not clarified *a priori* by this approach, in particular if such a pure Lie-group-based type of modelling is performed fully detached from empirical research. In this regard, special attention has to be given to the unclosed statistical equations of turbulence as considered herein, since the unclosed 2-point PDF in (1.1)-(1.2) is only an analytical and theoretical unknown, but not an empirical one since it is fully determined by the underlying deterministic Navier-Stokes equations, which again are well-known for to break statistical symmetries in turbulence within intermittent events (see e.g. Frisch (1995)). Hence extra caution has to be exercised when employing a pure symmetry-based modeling to turbulence.

goes without saying that if once a real solution for f_2 is known, and if the equivalence (1.24) itself is physically realizable,¹⁹ then this equivalence turns into a symmetry transformation and f_2 gets mapped to a new solution $\tilde{f}_2 = f_2 + \epsilon \cdot \eta_{f_2} + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)$. But since this is not the case here, any invariant transformation of (1.12)-(1.30) will thus at this stage only map between equations and not between solutions, where f_2 then is the unknown source or sink term, or collectively the unknown constitutive law of these equations.

Hence, for the global invariant scaling determined herein ($c_1^{11} = c_2^{11} = 0$) we cannot expect any information about the inner solution structure of the 1-point PDF equation as long as the dynamical equation for the 2-point PDF f_2 is not modeled. Without empirical modeling it is clear that the closure problem of turbulence cannot be circumvented by just employing the method of a Lie-group symmetry analysis. For more details on this issue, see e.g. Frewer *et al.* (2014a,b) and the references therein.

R5. Finally, it should not go unmentioned that Grebenev *et al.* (2017) & Waclawczyk *et al.* (2017) are not the first articles from the group of Oberlack *et al.* dealing with symmetries and the LMN equations which are flawed. The previously published comments by Frewer *et al.* (2014b, 2015a,b, 2016, 2017) and Frewer (2016) clearly prove this. Nor should it be ignored that the present flawed result of Grebenev *et al.* (2017) forms a basic building block of a recently granted 3-year DFG project (Gepriis, No. 385665358 [□](#)). A detailed critical discussion of this project is given in ResearchGate [□](#). In this regard please also visit <https://zenodo.org/communities/turbsym/>.

A. The general and full invariance group of the local equation \mathbf{E}_1 (1.4)

We present two different but equivalent versions as how one can perform a systematic and complete Lie-group invariance analysis of the local equation (1.4) using a software package, the DESOLV-II package of Vu *et al.* (2012).

In the first version (Version No.1), we consider the three dependent variables J^0, J^1, J^2 in (1.4) to explicitly depend on all independent variables of the system involved. These are seven in total and are listed in (1.3). Although we only consider here the local equation (1.4) and ignore in this step the non-local equations (1.5)-(1.8), we nevertheless should provide the symmetry searching algorithm with the information that three independent variables, namely $y^4 = x', y^5 = y', y^6 = \omega'$, are integration variables. This can be done by augmenting the local equation (1.4) with first-order differential consequences consistent with all equations (1.4)-(1.8) defining the system. The relevant ones are given by the system of equations $\partial_{y^j} J^k = 0$, for all $k = 0, 1, 2$ and $j = 4, 5, 6$, obviously telling us that all three dependent variables J^0, J^1, J^2 do not explicitly depend on the three (integration) variables y^4, y^5, y^6 , which brings us to the second version.

In the second version (Version No.2), we consider the three dependent variables J^0, J^1, J^2 in (1.4) to explicitly depend only on those independent variables which the full system (1.4)-(1.8) defines for them. As established in the first version above, they thus can only depend on the four variables y^0, y^1, y^2, y^3 . Hence, the symmetry analysis of this version will only involve a single equation, the local equation (1.4) itself.

As the computer results show below, *both* versions obviously yield exactly the same final result (1.9)-(1.11), in that the infinitesimal ξ^3 is only a function of ω , and this without any restrictions on the values of ω , as also stated correctly by (2.9).

¹⁹The equivalence transformation (1.24) is said to be physically realizable if the transformed field \tilde{f}_2 can be generated as a PDF-solution of the deterministic Navier-Stokes equations according to its transformation rule $\tilde{f}_2 = f_2 + \epsilon \cdot \eta_{f_2} + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)$, where we assume that the non-transformed field f_2 already constitutes a PDF-solution. In other words, if the transformed \tilde{f}_2 cannot emerge dynamically from the non-transformed f_2 via the deterministic and thus closed Navier-Stokes equations, then the equivalence (1.24) is nonphysical. To prove whether (1.24) is physically realizable or not, is beyond the scope of this article. However, there are a few examples of statistical Navier-Stokes equivalences which are clearly nonphysical — see e.g. Frewer *et al.* (2014b, 2015a, 2016, 2017); Sadeghi *et al.* (2020).

A.1. Version No. 1

Header:

```
> restart: read "Desolv-V5R5.mpl": with(desolv):
```

DESOLVII_V5R5 (March – 2011)(c)
by Dr. K. T. Vu, Dr. J. Carminati and Miss. G. Jefferson

Definitions of variables, local equation and differential consequences:

```
> alias(sigma=(y0,y1,y2,y3,y4,y5,y6,J0,J1,J2)): Y:=(y0,y1,y2,y3,y4,y5,y6):
> eqn0:=diff(J0(Y),y0)+diff(J1(Y),y1)+diff(J2(Y),y2)=0:
> eqn1:=diff(J0(Y),y4)=0: eqn2:=diff(J0(Y),y5)=0: eqn3:=diff(J0(Y),y6)=0:
eqn4:=diff(J1(Y),y4)=0: eqn5:=diff(J1(Y),y5)=0: eqn6:=diff(J1(Y),y6)=0:
eqn7:=diff(J2(Y),y4)=0: eqn8:=diff(J2(Y),y5)=0: eqn9:=diff(J2(Y),y6)=0:
> eqns:=[eqn0,eqn1,eqn2,eqn3,eqn4,eqn5,eqn6,eqn7,eqn8,eqn9]:
```

Symmetry Algorithm:

Size of the determining system:

```
> detsys:=gendef(eqns,[J0,J1,J2],[y0,y1,y2,y3,y4,y5,y6]): nops(detsys[1]);
45
```

Solving the determining system:

```
> sym:=pdesolv(op(detsys));
sym := [[ -\frac{\partial}{\partial y1}F_{-15}(y0,y1,y2,y3) - \frac{\partial}{\partial y2}F_{-21}(y0,y1,y2,y3) - F_{-47}(y0,y1,y2,y3),
\frac{\partial}{\partial y0}F_{-44}(y0,y1,y2,y3) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y1}F_{-45}(y0,y1,y2,y3) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y2}F_{-46}(y0,y1,y2,y3) ], [],
[\xi_{y0}(\sigma) = F_{-27}(y0,y1,y2,y3), \xi_{y1}(\sigma) = F_{-15}(y0,y1,y2,y3), \xi_{y2}(\sigma) = F_{-21}(y0,y1,y2,y3),
\xi_{y3}(\sigma) = F_{-9}(y3), \xi_{y4}(\sigma) = \xi_{y4}(\sigma), \xi_{y5}(\sigma) = \xi_{y5}(\sigma), \xi_{y6}(\sigma) = \xi_{y6}(\sigma),
\eta_{J0}(\sigma) = F_{-47}(y0,y1,y2,y3)J0 + J1 \frac{\partial}{\partial y1}F_{-27}(y0,y1,y2,y3)
+ J2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y2}F_{-27}(y0,y1,y2,y3) + F_{-44}(y0,y1,y2,y3),
\eta_{J1}(\sigma) = J0 \frac{\partial}{\partial y0}F_{-15}(y0,y1,y2,y3) + F_{-47}(y0,y1,y2,y3)J1 + J2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y2}F_{-15}(y0,y1,y2,y3)
+ J1 \frac{\partial}{\partial y1}F_{-15}(y0,y1,y2,y3) - J1 \frac{\partial}{\partial y0}F_{-27}(y0,y1,y2,y3) + F_{-45}(y0,y1,y2,y3),
\eta_{J2}(\sigma) = J0 \frac{\partial}{\partial y0}F_{-21}(y0,y1,y2,y3) + F_{-47}(y0,y1,y2,y3)J2 + J2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y2}F_{-21}(y0,y1,y2,y3)
+ J1 \frac{\partial}{\partial y1}F_{-21}(y0,y1,y2,y3) - J2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y0}F_{-27}(y0,y1,y2,y3) + F_{-46}(y0,y1,y2,y3) ],
[F_{-15}(y0,y1,y2,y3), F_{-21}(y0,y1,y2,y3), F_{-27}(y0,y1,y2,y3), F_{-44}(y0,y1,y2,y3),
F_{-45}(y0,y1,y2,y3), F_{-46}(y0,y1,y2,y3), F_{-47}(y0,y1,y2,y3), F_{-9}(y3),
\xi_{y4}(\sigma), \xi_{y5}(\sigma), \xi_{y6}(\sigma) ]]
```

Redefining solution functions as used in (1.9)-(1.11):

```

> F_27(y0,y1,y2,y3):=xi0(y0,y1,y2,y3); F_15(y0,y1,y2,y3):=xi1(y0,y1,y2,y3);
F_21(y0,y1,y2,y3):=xi2(y0,y1,y2,y3); F_9(y3):=xi3(y3);
F_47(y0,y1,y2,y3):=-diff(F_15(y0,y1,y2,y3),y1)-diff(F_21(y0,y1,y2,y3),y2);
F_44(y0,y1,y2,y3):=b0(y0,y1,y2,y3)-C(y3)*j0(y0,y1,y2,y3);
F_45(y0,y1,y2,y3):=b1(y0,y1,y2,y3)-C(y3)*j1(y0,y1,y2,y3);
F_46(y0,y1,y2,y3):=b2(y0,y1,y2,y3)-C(y3)*j2(y0,y1,y2,y3);

```

$$F_{27}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) := \xi_0(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3)$$

$$F_{15}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) := \xi_1(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3)$$

$$F_{21}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) := \xi_2(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3)$$

$$F_9(y_3) := \xi_3(y_3)$$

$$F_{47}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) := -\frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} \xi_1(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2} \xi_2(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3)$$

$$F_{44}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) := b_0(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - C(y_3) j_0(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3)$$

$$F_{45}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) := b_1(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - C(y_3) j_1(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3)$$

$$F_{46}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) := b_2(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - C(y_3) j_2(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3)$$

The arbitrary integration functions b_k and j_k are solutions of the local equation (1.4). Since (1.4) is a linear equation: if b_k and j_k are solutions, so is $B_k := b_k - C \cdot j_k$.

```

> simplify(sym[1,1]); simplify(sym[1,2])=0;

```

0

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y_0} b_0(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} b_1(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2} b_2(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - C(y_3) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial y_0} j_0(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} j_1(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2} j_2(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) \right) = 0$$

The solutions j^k can be identified as the dependent variables J^k :

```

> j0(y0,y1,y2,y3):=J0: j1(y0,y1,y2,y3):=J1: j2(y0,y1,y2,y3):=J2:

```

Final result which is identical to (1.9)-(1.11):

```

> simplify(sym[3,1]); simplify(sym[3,2]); simplify(sym[3,3]);
simplify(sym[3,4]); simplify(sym[3,8]); simplify(sym[3,9]);
simplify(sym[3,10]);

```

$$\xi_{y_0}(\sigma) = \xi_0(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3)$$

$$\xi_{y_1}(\sigma) = \xi_1(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3)$$

$$\xi_{y_2}(\sigma) = \xi_2(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3)$$

$$\xi_{y_3}(\sigma) = \xi_3(y_3)$$

$$\eta_{J_0}(\sigma) = J_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} \xi_0(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) + J_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2} \xi_0(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - J_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} \xi_1(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - J_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2} \xi_2(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - C(y_3) J_0 + b_0(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3)$$

$$\eta_{J_1}(\sigma) = J_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_0} \xi_1(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) + J_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2} \xi_1(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - J_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_0} \xi_0(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - J_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2} \xi_2(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - C(y_3) J_1 + b_1(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3)$$

$$\eta_{J_2}(\sigma) = J_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_0} \xi_2(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) + J_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} \xi_2(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - J_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_0} \xi_0(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - J_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} \xi_1(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - C(y_3) J_2 + b_2(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\eta_{J0}(\sigma) &= F_{-26}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) J_0 + J_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} F_{-3}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) \\
&\quad + J_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2} F_{-3}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) + F_{-23}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3), \\
\eta_{J1}(\sigma) &= J_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_0} F_{-6}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) + F_{-26}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) J_1 + J_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2} F_{-6}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) \\
&\quad + J_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} F_{-6}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - J_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_0} F_{-3}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) + F_{-24}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3), \\
\eta_{J2}(\sigma) &= J_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_0} F_{-9}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) + F_{-26}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) J_2 + J_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2} F_{-9}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) \\
&\quad + J_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} F_{-9}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - J_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y_0} F_{-3}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) + F_{-25}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) \Big], \\
&\quad \left[F_{-3}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3), F_{-6}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3), F_{-9}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3), F_{-23}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3), \right. \\
&\quad \left. F_{-24}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3), F_{-25}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3), F_{-26}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3), F_{-15}(y_3) \right] \Big]
\end{aligned}$$

This is exactly the same solution as obtained in Version No. 1. Just perform the following renaming,

$$\begin{aligned}
F_{-3} \rightarrow F_{-27} &=: \xi_0, \quad F_{-6} \rightarrow F_{-15} =: \xi_1, \quad F_{-9} \rightarrow F_{-21} =: \xi_2, \quad F_{-15} \rightarrow F_{-9} =: \xi_3, \\
F_{-23} \rightarrow F_{-44}, \quad F_{-24} \rightarrow F_{-45}, \quad F_{-25} \rightarrow F_{-46}, \quad F_{-26} \rightarrow F_{-47}
\end{aligned}$$

then solve for F_{47} , and finally identify the three functions F_{44} , F_{45} and F_{46} again as

$$\begin{aligned}
F_{-44}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) &:= b_0(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - C(y_3) J_0(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) \\
F_{-45}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) &:= b_1(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - C(y_3) J_1(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) \\
F_{-46}(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) &:= b_2(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3) - C(y_3) J_2(y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3)
\end{aligned}$$

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